

The methanol extract on tlc examination (chloroform-methanol-water; 35 : 13.5 : 1.8) showed three brown spots under uv light. They were separated by preparative-tlc and labelled as BLG-I to BLG-III, in order of increasing R_f values.

Compound BLG-I: It was crystallised from methanol-benzene as yellow cubes, m.p. 228°. Shinoda and Molisch test showed it to be a flavonol glycoside. On acid hydrolysis it gave an aglycone, m.p. 276–78°, characterised as kaempferol by comparison of its m.p., uv and nmr spectra with that of authentic sample. The sugar was found to be glucose by R_f values on co-pc with authentic sugars. BLG-I showed a slight hypsochromic shift while its aglycone revealed a bathochromic shift of 9 nm (from 266 to 275 nm) with NaOAc, showing the attachment of sugar at C-7 of the kaempferol. The identity of BLG-I as kaempferol-7-*O*-glucoside was further supported by the hydrolysis of permethylated glycoside. The partial methyl ether obtained was identified as 3', 4', 5'-trimethoxykaempferol by m.p. and m.m.p. with an authentic sample (m.p. 151°)⁶.

Compound BLG-II: It was a yellow solid, m.p. 272° and gave positive Shinoda and Molisch test. On acid hydrolysis, it gave an aglycone, m.p. 315° and a sugar. The aglycone was identified as quercetin by direct comparison with an authentic sample and also by uv spectral studies. The sugar was identified as rhamnose by co-pc with authentic sugars. The uv spectral data of BLG-II showed the presence of free 3-OH, 5-OH and 3',4'-orthodihydroxyl groups with classical shift reagents. Hydrolysis of permethylated glycoside gave 3,5,3',4'-tetramethylquercetin⁶, m.p. 284°, and was characterised by comparison with an authentic sample. The formation of the above tetramethyl ether confirmed the attachment of sugar at C-7 hydroxyl group. BLG-II was thus characterised as quercetin-7-*O*-rhamnoside.

Compound BLG-III: It was a bright yellow solid, m.p. 191–92° and gave positive Shinoda and Molisch test. The uv spectral data in the presence of classical shift reagents indicated the presence of free hydroxyl groups at C-5 and C-7 besides 3',4'-orthodihydroxyl groups⁷ and glycosylation at C-3. Total hydrolysis of BLG-III with 10% alcoholic HCl gave quercetin, glucose and rhamnose, and was identified by R_f value, m.p., m.m.p. spectral data and co-pc with authentic samples. The partial hydrolysis of BLG-III with 1% aqueous H₂SO₄ for 1 h gave a glucoside, BLG-III_{pg} and rhamnose. BLG-III_{pg} on further hydrolysis yielded quercetin and glucose thereby indicating rhamnose to be the terminal sugar. Methylation of BLG-III by Hakomori's method followed by acid hydrolysis gave 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl-1-rhamnose, 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl-D-glucose and an aglycone characterised as quercetin 5,7,3',4'-tetramethyl ether (m.p. 193°). On the basis of the above facts BLG-III was characterised as quercetin-3-*O*-rhamnoglucoside (rutin).

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2-Amino-4-phenyl-5-phenylazothiazole as an Analytical Reagent for Spectrophotometric Determination of Iron(III)

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THE title compound gives dark red colour with iron(III), the intensity of which is not affected by the ions which generally cause interference in case of other reagents reported¹. The 1 : 2 (metal-reagent) complex absorbs at λ 480 nm, away from the absorbance maxima of the reagent itself (450 nm). The reagent is very sensitive and the determination straightforward, which is an indication of the betterment in the direction of the search of a more suitable reagent for iron(III) determinations in micro analysis.

The reagent was synthesised as reported earlier². Sodium nitrite (1.4 g, 0.02 mol) dissolved in water (25 ml) was gradually added to a well-cooled solution of aniline (1.85 g, 0.02 mol) in 3 *N* HCl (2.5 ml). The diazonium salt solution was filtered to a cold suspension of 2-amino-4-phenylthiazole (3.5 g, 0.02 mol) and sodium acetate (5 g) in ethanol (50 ml). After constant stirring for 0.5 h the mixture was left for 2 h. 2-Amino-4-phenyl-5-phenylazothiazole precipitated was filtered, washed several times with water and recrystallised as red needles from DMF-ethanol mixture (1 : 1), m.p. 195°.

Absorbance measurements at varying wavelengths were recorded with a Unicam SP-500 spectrophotometer using 1-cm path-length matched glass cuvettes. pH measurements were made with a ECIL 823 pH meter.

Procedure: To an aliquot containing 100–400 μ g of iron(III) was added 0.01 *M* reagent (1.0 ml) and then diluted to 25 ml with the buffer solution (pH 3.0; sodium acetate-HCl). The absorbance was measured at 480 nm using ethanol as reference.

Vosburgh and Cooper's method³ indicated the formation of only one complex and the presence

of one maxima at 480 nm. pH was varied with the buffer. The most suitable pH lies in the range 2.4–3.0. The maximum absorbance was observed in presence of three-fold excess of the reagent. The complex obeyed Beer's law upto 40 ppm Fe^{III}. The optimum concentration range for 1-cm cell was evaluated by Ringbom⁴ plot which was found to be 16–30 ppm Fe^{III}. Sensitivity of determination and molar absorptivity were 0.048 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ and $1.06 \times 10^5 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively. The combining ratio of iron(III) and the reagent was 1 : 2. The stability constant of the complex was determined by molar-ratio method and was found to be $4.80 \times 10^{12} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$.

The interference caused by various ions, viz. Na^I, K^I, Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Sr^{II}, Ba^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Hg^{II}, Tl^I, Ag^I, La^{III}, Sb^{III}, As^{III}, Bi^{III}, VO^{II}, Cr^{III}, UO₂^{II}, Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Rh^{III}, Pd^{II}, chloride, bromide, iodide, acetate, carbonate, sulphite, sulphate, nitrite, nitrate, thiosulphate, cyanide, borate, thiocyanate, persulphate, salicylate and ascorbic acid do not interfere even when present to five-fold excess. However, the excess of fluoride and phosphate seriously interfere.

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Selective Detection of NCS⁻ with Bismuth Nitrate by Capillary Solid-state Spot-tests

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SEVERAL methods¹ have been developed for detection, determination and separation of thiocyanate in solution, but no attempt has been made to detect NCS⁻ in solid-state. Capillary solid-state spot-test technique developed in our laboratory² provides three variables, such as the colour at the junction, the direction of movement of the coloured boundary and the length of the coloured boundary. These variables make a test more selective than wet

and powder trituration spot-tests in which only the colour formed is indicative.

Therefore, an attempt has been made to develop a selective solid-state spot-test for NCS⁻ using bismuth nitrate as reagent and allowing the reaction to occur through a glass-wool plug via vapour phase diffusion.

Experimental

Bismuth nitrate (BN) and ammonium thiocyanate (ATC) were of AnalaR grade. Anions such as Fe(CN)₆⁴⁻, Fe(CN)₆³⁻, Cr₂O₇²⁻, CrO₄²⁻, S₂O₈²⁻, BrO₃⁻, NO₃⁻, VO₃⁻, Br⁻ and I⁻ were of AnalaR grade and taken as their sodium or potassium salts. Chlorides of copper, iron and tin, acetate of zinc and nitrate of chromium were used. Intimate mixture of variable concentrations of well-powdered reagent were prepared with strontium nitrate as diluent. The mixture was trituated in a small mortar till it became homogeneous.

Solid-state detection by powder trituration: The test material (6–10 mg) was trituated with well-powdered reagent in the depression of a white spot-plate, and the colour developed at room temperature (30°) was recorded.

Detection by capillary solid-state tests: The well-powdered reagent was introduced from one end of a graduated capillary (10 cm × 2.5 mm dia) and the test material was similarly packed from the other end in order to bring both the reactants into close contact in the middle of the capillary. The grinding and packing of powders were done in a reproducible manner. The colour at the junction, the direction of the movement and length of the coloured boundary were recorded at desired temperature after a fixed time interval. To study the effect of concentration of reagent on the length and direction of the coloured boundary, synthetic mixtures containing 1–10% BN with strontium nitrate were filled in capillaries in place of pure BN as described above.

Glass-wool plug modification for specific detection of NCS⁻: An air gap between the reagent and the test material was created by introducing a glass-wool plug (2–6 mm) in the middle of the glass capillary before the filling of reactants into it. The test material and the reagent were then filled from either ends of the capillary. The colour and thickness of the coloured boundary formed at glass-wool test material junction were recorded.

Results and Discussion

The anions like Cl⁻, HCO₃⁻, IO₃⁻, IO₄⁻, CH₃COO⁻, HCOO⁻, CQ₃²⁻, MoO₄²⁻, SO₃²⁻, S₂²⁻, SO₄²⁻, C₂O₄²⁻ and PO₄²⁻ did not give any colour with BN when trituated on a spot plate at 30°. All these anions except HCOO⁻ produced white precipitate in solution. Cations like Hg₂²⁺, Ag⁺, Cd²⁺, Ba²⁺, Ca²⁺,